

PROFILE, INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) COMPETENCE, AND CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY PUBLIC SCHOOL PROFICIENT TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the difference in Information and Communications Technology (ICT) competence of selected teachers when grouped according to age, gender, education, specialization, teaching position, experience, and training. Employing quantitative and qualitative approaches using frequency and percent counts, 5-point Likert scale, test of difference, and thematic analysis, it surfaced that the teachers are generally advance in ICT use. Also, among the profile variables, it is only on gender grouping that their ICT competence level indicated no significant difference. Meanwhile, limited internet connectivity, lack of material, financial, and human support, and insufficient training opportunities emerged as the major struggles of the teachers in progressing their ICT competence. In conclusion, teachers can achieve proficiency in ICT use if only the national and local government, partner agencies, and they themselves will altogether strengthen their related programs, and when each one commits to beat the fast-growing trends in global education.

Keywords: *ICT competence, internet connection, gender, proficiency, profile, teachers*

INTRODUCTION

The competencies of the teachers are being updated on the new trends, innovations, and knowledge to enhance their teaching methods to address the 21st Century Education challenges. To create learning environment that is interactive and engaging for the development of student's digital literacy skills, collaboration in learning

and critical thinking skills, is based on the competence of teachers (UNESCO ICT Competency Framework for Teachers, 2008). Moreover, as Mumcu (2022) stated, in the formal and informal learning, the importance of technology is increasing and it is important that teachers should have the competencies to effectively integrate technology in the classroom to provide quality education in the global setting.

Finally, meeting the objective of integrating technology inside the classroom, pedagogical knowledge of teachers should be developed, and skills in ICT for instructions and new technologies are being adapted, and their ICT competencies should be refined to effectively integrate technological instructions (Wei et al., 2016).

As such, the Department of Education (DepEd) has been strengthening its initiatives in mitigating the extreme needs of teachers all over the country in enhancing their teaching performance. On February 03, 2023, the agency has issued DepEd Memorandum No. 008, s. 2023, otherwise known as Multi-Year Guidelines on the Results-Based Performance Management System-Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (RPMS-PPST) which encloses the detailed procedure and information on the adoption and implementation of performance management and appraisal of teachers, consistent with DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015 also known as “Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) in the Department of Education (DepEd) and pursuant to Section 5 of DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 which provides for the “National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), which mandates that all performance appraisals for teachers shall be based on this set of standards.

With this standard tool for appraisal, Teachers I-III are being observed to perform classroom sessions once every quarter, aiming to gain the highest rating of seven (7) in each of the indicators, including the “The teacher selected, develop, organized, and used appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.” However, per the National ICT Competency Standard (NICS) Basic of the Commission on Information and Communications Technology (CICT), encoding, use of powerpoint, and utilization of digital and digitized learning materials and resources are simply basic skills which each in the education sector must possess.

This prompted the researcher to investigate the difference in ICT competence of selected teachers when grouped according to age, gender, education, specialization, teaching position, experience, and training, as well as their struggles in their attempt to improve their teaching practice involving ICT use.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study was sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the proficient teachers in terms of age, gender, field of specialization, highest education attainment, plantilla/teaching position, number of

- ICT-related seminars and trainings attended, and number of years of teaching experience?
2. What is the level of Information Communication Technology (ICT) competence of the respondents?
 3. Is there a significant difference on the level of Information ICT competence of the respondents when grouped according to the profile variables?
 4. What are the challenges being encountered by the teacher respondents along enhancing their ICT competence?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed quantitative descriptive approach for it determined and described the current level of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competence among public-school teachers based on the Skill Set Divisions of the National ICT Competency Standard (NICS) Basic, which include the following competencies: ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheets, Presentation, Information and Communication, Computer Ethics and Security.

The quantitative-descriptive aspect involved the analysis required for the profile variables and the ICT competence level. Test of difference was specifically utilized in this part. Moreover, qualitative approach was also employed since the personal perceptions, thoughts, views, and experiences of the respondents were thematically analyzed through axial coding; then the responses were thematically discussed.

Research Locale

The research locale is a typical district of elementary and secondary schools located in a rural community of the province. Like most districts, it is being headed by a District-In-Charge who governs elementary schools of different contexts. Others are typically regular; others are multi-grade, others big, small, and large in terms of populations. There is also an active Alternative Learning System (ALS) being handled by DepEd Teachers. Teachers are diverse also. Others hail from the locality while others are not. Some are seasoned; others are new. Learners are diverse, too. Most belong to the IP groups belonging in different cultural communities, but there are also considerable number of Tagalogs and Ilokanos. Others are children of the locality; others are movers in.

Research Participants

The primary focus of the study were those teachers employed with the teaching/platilla positions of Teacher I, Teacher II, and Teacher III (Proficient Teachers per RPMS-PPST) in the secondary and elementary schools in the District of Santa Fe, Schools Division of Nueva Vizcaya for the academic year 2023-2024. The respondents,

selected through total enumeration sampling, were composed of a total of one hundred sixty-four (164) teacher-respondents.

Research Instrument

A structured survey questionnaire adapted from the National ICT Competency Standards (NICS) Basic produced by the Commission on Information and Communications Technology (CICT) was used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into three (3) parts. The first part intended to collect the profile of the respondents which included the age, sex, highest education attainment, field of specialization, teaching position, number of ICT-related seminars and trainings attended, and number of years of experience in teaching. Assessment of competence in particular skill set divisions described in NICS-Basic was the focus of the second part of the survey questionnaire. These Skill Set Divisions include ICT Basics, Word Processing, Spreadsheets, Presentation, Information and Communication, and Computer Ethics and Security.

Finally, the end part was checklist of possible challenges of which the respondents have chosen from. Next to the checklist were blanks where they have expressed and elaborated their responses in a free-flowing manner, at their own language preferences. As necessary, follow up interview from a few respondents was conducted to validate and clarify responses through in-person and remote modalities.

Data Gathering Procedure

To get to the process of data gathering, the researcher wrote letters requesting for the approval from the Schools Division of Nueva Vizcaya Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisor and the Teachers-in-Charge and School Heads. Also, letters of permission to conduct the study was forwarded to have access to the respondents. The survey questionnaire was subjected to proper expert validation, particularly on Parts I and III. When ready, a copy of the questionnaire was personally handed by the researcher to each of the respondents to ensure hundred percent data collection from the target respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The succeeding discussion details the profile of the teacher respondents in terms of age, gender, field of specialization, highest education attainment, plantilla or teaching position, number of ICT-related seminars and training attended, and number of years of teaching experience, respectively.

The table that follows present the frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of age.

Table 1: Frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of age

Age	f	%
56-60	13	7.93
51-55	5	3.05
46-50	19	11.59
41-45	32	19.51
36-40	29	17.68
31-35	25	15.24
26-30	38	23.17
21-25	3	1.83
Total	164	100.00

The respondents' ages are distributed from at least 21 years old to the retirement age, 60 years old, which could mean that some of the proficient teachers in the district are young and others are seasoned teachers. Only three teachers or 1.83 percent belong to the 21-25 age bracket; only five or 3.05 percent are aged 51-55 years old; and majority are from age 26-50; while 13 or nearly eight percent belong to the 56-60 years old bracket or 'retirement' age bracket.

Concludingly, majority of the Proficient Teachers in the district are not new in the teaching profession but some are young, others are at mid-age, and the rest are nearing retirement.

This finds similarity and support from the findings of Elli & Ricafort (2020), as cited by Sanchez et al. (2022). They have established that teachers of younger ages are more eager to learn more about teaching, and are better at computers and technology. Also, they asserted that age has significant impact on the ICT skills of the teachers.

Table 2: Frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of sex

Sex	f	%
Male	30	18.29
Female	134	81.71
Total	164	100.00

In terms of sex, only 30 or 18.29 percent are males while 134 or 81.71 percent are females which could be inferred to mean that majority of the Proficient Teachers in Santa Fe District are boys, and that female teachers are outnumbered by almost 82 percent.

Similar to this undertaking, Mijares (2022) also considered gender in his study titled "Teachers' Information and Communication Technology Competencies: The Basis for a Competency-based Training Plan." He found out that significant difference was not established in their gender, so with some other profile variables.

Table 3: Frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of field of specialization

Field of Specialization	f	%
Science	21	12.80
Mathematics	9	5.49
English	20	12.20
Filipino	11	6.71
MAPEH	6	3.66
Araling Panlipunan	11	6.71
EsP/Values Education	0	0.00
EPP/TLE/TVL	20	12.20
General	66	40.24
Total	164	100.00%

On the other hand, per observation on the succeeding table, it can be seen that there are no Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao or Values Education (EsP/VE) Proficient Teachers in the research locale but 66 or 40.24 percent are generalists, which could mean that they comprise most, if not all, the Elementary Proficient Teacher respondents.

Those who specialized in English and Edukasyong Pantahanan at Pangkabuhayan and/or Technology and Livelihood Education/Technical Vocational Livelihood compose the 40 or 24.40 of the respondents and 21 or 12.80 percent specialized in Science. It could mean further that those who have indicated their specializations are the respondents drawn to represent the Secondary School Proficient Teachers comprising at least 60 percent of the total research respondents. This means that that the teachers are capable of teaching all the subjects being offered in both elementary and secondary levels. While none specialized in EsP or VE or its allies, is still being taught since values, as always said, are not necessarily learned in school but are acquired of which every teacher must be able to deliver in class the necessary competencies.

Though no recent studies have been found to corroborate with the foregoing finding, Hussain et al. (2017) established that ICT in learning institutions provides opportunities to educators to transform their teaching practices by providing them with improved educational content and more effective instructional techniques, regardless of specialization.

Table 4: Frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of highest education attainment

Highest Education Attainment	F	%
Bachelor's Degree	61	37.20
Completed Academic Units in Master's Degree	95	57.93
Master's Degree	6	3.66
Completed Academic Units in Doctoral Degree	2	1.22
Doctoral Degree	0	0.00
Total	164	100.00

Nearly 60 percent of the respondents have completed academics units in their Master's Degree; only six or 3.66 percent have finished and completed their Master's education; and only two or 1.22 percent have completed academic units in their Doctoral

Degree. None among the 164 teacher respondents have completed any Doctoral Degree. Furthermore, nearly 40 percent of them have not pursued any post graduate education after holding their Bachelor's degree diplomas. Despite nearing the retirement age of at least 20 percent of the teacher, and despite the big number (at most 80 percent) of the teachers being young in the teaching profession, they have not sought professional advancement along education.

The result corroborates with Sanchez et al. (2022) who cited that Elli & Ricafort (2020) contended that teachers with masters and doctoral degree, and other advanced studies have significant effect on student achievement, which this research finds association on to teachers' ICT use and performance. Also, they asserted that educational attainment has significant impact on the ICT skills of the teachers.

Table 5: Frequency and percent distribution of the respondents when grouped in terms of plantilla or teaching position

Plantilla Position	f	%
Teacher I	36	21.95
Teacher II	20	12.20
Teacher III	108	65.85
Total	164	100.00

There are 108 or 65.85 percent Teacher III respondents; 36 or 21.95 percent are Teacher I; and 20 or 12.20 percent are Teacher II. This means that more than half of the respondents hold the highest position in the Proficient Teacher category per PPST-RPMS. The teachers are looking forward onto possibilities of promotion in the next few years while the large number of Teacher III plantilla holders may soon become Highly Proficient Teachers (Master Teacher I-IV) per RPMS-PPST.

This study is likened to the work of Sanchez et al. (2022) who studied that profile, including teaching position are strong predictors of the ICT competence of teachers. Also, they asserted that plantilla position has significant impact on the ICT skills of the teachers.

Table 6: Frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of number of ICT-related seminars and training attended

Number of ICT-Related Seminars and Training Attended	F	%
1	89	54.27
2	32	19.51
3	13	7.93
4	6	3.66
5	3	1.83
6 or more	21	12.80
Total	164	100.00

Eighty-nine (89) or 54.27 percent of the respondents have attended only one ICT-related seminar or training which could be inferred to mean that more than half of the

Proficient Teacher respondents have not been given the opportunity to attend several learning and development activities or programs along ICT.

Furthermore, 32 or 19.51 percent have attended two ICT-related seminars/training while the rest of the teachers have attended three or more. In fact, 21 or 12.80 percent have been participants in 6 or more training or seminars related to ICT. As such, the teachers have had limited ICT-related training and seminars. They need more learning and development programs along ICT skills development, especially in this contemporary era of rapid technological advancement, truly crucial in the teaching and learning processes.

However, according to the findings of Mijares (2022), a significant difference in teachers' ICT competence was not established in number of ICT-related training attended, so with other profile variables like gender, age, educational attainment, position, and years of using ICT in teaching, which this foregoing study has established the other way, as seen in the succeeding discussions.

Table 7: Frequency and percent distribution of the respondents in terms of number of years of teaching experience

Number of Years of Teaching Experience	F	%
1	7	4.27
2	8	4.88
3	8	4.88
4	7	4.27
5	13	7.93
6 or more	121	73.78
Total	164	100.00

As to teaching experience, nearly one-fourth of the participants as indicated by the frequency of 121 or 73.78 percent have been in teaching for 6 or more years and 13 or 7.93 percent have been teaching for five years. Meanwhile, the rest of the respondents have been with the teaching profession for seven to eight years now. At least 80 percent of the teacher respondents have gained recognizable experience in teaching pupils and students, and are not necessarily behind nor ignorant about how ICT plays a significant role in both formal and informal education in the country and worldwide.

In relation to the findings, Mijares (2020) established that a significant difference in teachers' ICT competence was found in the length of their teaching service.

Table 8: Summary of the level of Information Communication Technology (ICT) competence of the respondents

Information Communication Technology (ICT) Indicator Set	Over-all Mean	Verbal Description
ICT Basics	3.6128	Advance
Word Processing	4.2947	Advance
Spreadsheet	3.5556	Advance
Presentation	3.7663	Advance
Communication & Information	3.5047	Advance
Computer Ethics and Security	3.4286	Intermediate
Grand Mean	3.6938	Advance

1.00-1.40=Fundamental; 1.50-2.49=Basic; 2.50-3.49=Intermediate; 3.50-4.49=Advance; 4.50-5.00=Proficient

The teacher respondents' level of ICT competence is advance as indicated by the obtained grand mean of 3.6938. However, it can be noted that the teachers gained an over-all mean of 3.4286 in the ICT indicator set Computer Ethics which is the only category with a verbal description of intermediate, among others, which could be interpreted to mean that it is necessary for them and the department to address such learning need.

On the other hand, it is worth noting that the first five sets of skills indicators gained means that are equivalent to advance level, with Word Processing (4.2947) bearing the highest over-all mean, respectively followed by Presentation (3.7663), ICT Basics (3.6128), Spreadsheet (3.5556), and Communication & Information (3.5047).

The finding finds support from Hariany et al. (2021) who contend that possessing digital competencies in the integration of ICT in classroom practices should be a need because in this global education system, the teachers' competence in ICT is essential to the outcomes of learning which is reiterated by Napalit et al. (2021) in claiming that in the 21st century education, teachers play a crucial role in developing knowledge and skills, which is undoubtedly supported by Hariany et al. (2021) for they affirm that skilled teachers in ICT can appropriately incorporate digital tools and digital resources in their lessons and create a learning environment that is more dynamic and give students an interactive experience in learning.

Meanwhile, the results of the investigation of Correos (2014), in his context, focused on the "Teachers' ICT Literacy and Utilization in English Language Teaching" bared that the teachers' ICT literacy was moderate. As a generalization drawn from the finding, teachers, especially the Proficient Teachers, must be provided with relevant ICT skills enhancement seminars and training.

Table 9: Difference on the level of Information Communication Technology (ICT) competence of the respondents when grouped according to the profile variables

Source of Variation	SSb	SSw	dfb	dfw	MSb	MSw	F	p	F crit	QD
Age	192.77	62.05	7	440	27.54	0.14	195.29	0.00*	2.03	Sig.
Gender	0.00	11.16	1	110	0.00	0.10	0.04	0.83	3.93	Not Sig.
Specialization	19.27	62.88	7	440	2.75	0.14	19.26	0.00*	2.03	Sig.
Highest Education Attainment	45.55	32.16	3	220	15.18	0.15	103.87	0.00*	2.65	Sig.
Plantilla Position	6.68	24.20	2	2	3.34	0.15	22.76	0.00*	3.05	Sig.
No. of ICT-Related L&D Attended	85.80	41.54	5	330	17.16	0.13	136.34	0.00*	2.24	Sig.
No. of Years of Teaching Experience	8.95	51.02	5	330	1.79	0.15	11.58	0.00*	2.24	Sig.

alpha level=0.05

QD=qualitative description

F=computed F-value p=computed p-value

Only the profile “gender” obtained a p-value (0.83) which is equivalent to a not significant difference qualitative description among all other profile variables analyzed in this study. This means that there is no significant difference in the ICT competence of the teacher-respondents when grouped according to gender at 0.05 alpha level. In such a case, the null hypothesis is accepted.

It is also observed that the ICT competence of the teachers significantly differ when grouped according to age, specialization, plantilla position, highest education attainment, number of ICT-related seminars and training attended, and number of years of teaching experience, as indicated by the computed p-value of 0.00* at 5% level of significance, all indicating that the null hypothesis is rejected.

The result of the analysis could generally be interpreted to mean that demographic profile could be significant determiners of one’s level of ICT competence.

Conversely, ICT competence level, in this case, did not result in any anticipated significant difference when the respondents were grouped according to gender, which is parallel to the study of Mijares (2022) titled Teachers’ Information and Communication Technology Competencies: The Basis for a Competency-based Training Plan. His finding has not established any significant difference in terms of their gender, so with other variables like age, educational attainment, position, number of ICT-related training, and years of using ICT in teaching, but has found in the teachers’ length of teaching service.

The result also finds both similarities and differences in the finding of Dela Fuente & Biñas (2020) who established that age, gender, the highest educational attainment, field of specialization and the teaching position in different skill-set like the ICT-basics, word processing, spreadsheet, presentation, information and communication, and computer ethics and security have no significant difference in the teachers’ ICT competence. They stated further that their finding is being supported by the assertions of Jegede (2009) that age does not affect the time used of ICT when attitude, competence,

and use pattern of teachers are considered. Moreover, it was found out in their study that female teachers have more negative attitudes towards computers than men.

The finding of Fuente & Biñas (2020) mentioned further that the General Linear Model (GLM) analysis emphasized that on computer use, gender has a significant effect, self-perceived computer experience, computer anxiety attitude, and student interaction, as cited in Broos (2005), according to them. So, for them, the success of ICT integration in the classroom relies on the willingness of teachers to adapt to change, acquire reasonable ICT competencies, and demonstrate effective time management skills.

Similarly, Correos (2014) uncovered evidence about the scarceness of ICT in language teaching and that teachers faced numerous challenges that discourage them from using ICT in teaching. He then recommended the following: 1) the need to afford teachers with intensive ICT-based trainings to furnish them with ICT knowledge and its imperative contribution in language education; 2) school leaders and stakeholders may source out interventions to advance school's resources; and 3) a grander school level ICT development plan be implemented to guarantee rationality of ICT implementation in the educative process.

Based on the commonality of the responses, there established several challenges that the respondents encountered that hinder them from enhancing their ICT competence. These are: limited network connection, lack of human, material, and financial resources, lack of training opportunities, limited technical support, and lack of motivation and other needed supports.

Conclusions

Based on the research findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Proficient Teachers in a particular district comprise a representation of Teacher I, Teacher II, and Teacher III, all of diverse ages, sex/gender, fields of expertise, and education; varied number and nature of professional development engagements; and sundry length of experience in teaching.
2. Proficient Teachers' level of ICT competence may vary in each of the categorized indicators, but when perceived in a general view, they have not reached the highest level of competence yet, which could further indicate a need for more skills training while they are simultaneously fulfilling their teaching roles and responsibilities to their clientele – the learners.
3. One's level of ICT competence may differ from one another because of some personological and demographic profiles like age, education, specialization, teaching position, exposure, and experience, but not necessarily because of gender difference.

4. Proficient Teachers' encounter various problems making them struggle in increasing the level of their ICT competence. Some of these problems are attributed to poor internet connectivity, scarcity of all types of personal and non-personal resources, limited learning and training opportunities, and lack of self-initiative.

Recommendations

The findings and inferences drawn from this study prompted the researcher to recommend the following:

1. Since every learning institution is comprised of diverse teachers in terms of age, gender, position, education, specialization, experience, training, and the like, the education agency must provide all-inclusive, needs-responsive, and equal opportunities to them, especially in providing avenues for professional growth and development for them to also sustain a good living.
2. Each teacher, through the support of the agency and the administrators, must initiate and find ways and means to achieve professional growth and development. This can be done by self-initiated actions, added with mandated ones. Teachers may undergo self-initiated training enroll in short courses, and/or pursue post graduate education and advance skills trainings.
3. In the midst of individual differences, each one in the academe should be given the equal learning and training opportunities, be provided with their basic needs to improve their skills and competence, and for them to make a difference in their teaching careers, especially in training students with lifelong skills. As such, the education department and ICT training providers should collaborate in providing ample training opportunities to all teachers.
4. Poor internet connectivity, scarcity of all types of personal and non-personal resources, limited learning and training opportunities, and lack of self-initiative should be the top priority of school administrators and benefactors for funding and sourcing out of other resources.
5. School administrators must strengthen its initiatives in adhering to the guidelines of the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP) and other government-funded initiatives of providing strong internet connection to their respective schools so that as the teachers deliver the necessary competencies and skills to their learners by integrating ICT and ICT-aided instruction, they also, hand in hand, gradually improve themselves in terms of ICT use. Moreover, similar DepEd and other providers should not only offer ICT-related seminars/training to School DCP and ICT Coordinators, but also to all the teachers across positions. If there is also a great possibility, DepEd may adopt and use the National ICT Competency Standards (NICS) Basic Skill Sets in appraising teachers' ICT competence on the aspect of ICT integration to teaching practice and to students' learning

engagements, side by side the RPMS-PPST. Also, DepEd, particularly those zero/poor signal and visibility schools, may heighten their partnership initiatives and linkages with internet service and network providers for them to acquire the least to best possibility of internet connectivity, as well as acquisition of ICT materials, equipment, and gadgets.

6. Local Government Units and other DepEd benefactors, private or public, may include in their Special Fund for Education (SEF) or however they say it, the provision, acquisition, and/or purchase of ICT materials to augment the limited teacher and school resources.
7. In-charge of plotting teaching loads of teachers may consider allotting ample time schedules for ICT-expert teachers to provide technical assistance and support to their fellow teachers and employees who lack the necessary ICT skills and competence. When not so much loaded, they may have the leeway of time and opportunity to peer train those who need the necessary training on ICT.
8. Teachers, especially if financially capable, may seek for providers of ICT training their current institution cannot provide so that they will not be left behind by the fast-growing advancement in ICT. Doing such could provide them the opportunity to grow themselves professionally without relying much from the agency nor wasting so much time from awaiting uncertain opportunities to come along.
9. Professional development training providers such as DOST, DICT, CICT and others may extent their programs to DepEd teachers who by research-driven data have no or with limited training and seminars attended related to ICT use and operation.
10. Future researchers may use this study as reference and as source of information. They may also engage in similar or related research, replicating and/or considering the variables not analyzed in this study, in other contexts, and exploring other relevant areas which have been the limitations of this research.
11. DepEd, particularly the schools, DICT, and other training providers may consider utilizing, adopting, and or enhancing the appended ICT Training Matrix for Teachers developed by the researcher himself as an offshoot of this research, in crafting and in initiating ICT-related trainings for teachers.

Proposed ICT Training Matrix for Teachers

Time	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5
7:00-7:30 AM	Management of Learning (MOL)	Management of Learning (MOL)	Management of Learning (MOL)	Management of Learning (MOL)	Management of Learning (MOL)
7:30-8:30 AM	Registration of Participants	Plenary 3: Spreadsheet - Excel Formulas and Functions	Plenary 6: Computer Security and Ethics - Software piracy - copy right laws - cyber security	Are you afraid of AI? - Artificial Intelligence	Use of Productivity Tools - Video, Audio, Picture
8:30-9:30 AM	Opening Program				
9:30-10:00 AM	HEALTH BREAK				
10:00AM-12:00 NN	Plenary 1: ICT Basic -Hardware -Software - Networking and Communications Technology	Plenary 4: Presentation -Avance MS Power point presentation animation and audio recording	Hands-on Activity	Advance Technological Tools in Teaching	Hands-on Activity
12:00 NN-1:00 PM	HEALTH BREAK				
1:00-3:00 PM	Plenary 2: Word Processing - MS Word Advance (Mail Merge)	Plenary 5: Information and Communication - World Wide Web - Bookmarks - Address Book	Presentation of Outputs Plenary 1 to 6	ICT in the 21 st Century	Presentation of Outputs
3:00-3:30 PM	HEALTH BREAK				
3:30-5:00 PM	Hands-on Activity	Hands-on Activity	Hands-on Activity	Hands-on Activity	Closing Program

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirmed confidentiality of the data collected from the respondents. Accuracy and integrity were guaranteed during the process of data gathering. Inconsistencies were rectified as soon as possible. Throughout the whole process of data collection, ethical standards were adhered to, with a particular focus on the significance of voluntary participation, informed consent, and respect to the rights and privacy of the respondents. Following the completion of the retrieval of the survey, the data were analyzed using the proper statistical methods.

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